

STEP BY STEP IDEA PLANNER FOR EFFECTOR TRIAL VIDEOS

Video Title: _____

Instructions: This template will help you formulate your ideas for creating the **EFFECTOR Trial Video** and better plan your actions towards its realization. It is a step by step template where in **Step 1** you draft what you want to present in your video. In **step 2**, you identify how are you going to structure the video and in **Step 3** you note down in detail what will you need (text, footage, etc.) in regards to the structure you created in step 2.

Step 1	Description of the _____ EFFECTOR Trial <i>(Portuguese EFFECTOR Trial, French EFFECTOR Trial, Greek EFFECTOR Trial)</i>	Step 2	Structure <i>(what is needed)</i>
<p><i>What to present – please write a summary (draft your ideas):</i></p> <div style="text-align: center; font-size: 4em; opacity: 0.1; font-weight: normal;">EFFECTOR</div>		<p><i>How are you going to present the EFFECTOR trial? By using:</i></p> <p>A] Interview format given by partner: Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> <i>Description: Question is asked – a partner replies</i></p> <p>B] Narration: Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> <i>Description: A partner describes in front of the camera aspects of the EFFECTOR pilot.</i></p> <p>C] Video shooting during the EFFECTOR trial: Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> <i>Description: Video will be taken from the activities during EFFECTOR trial</i></p> <p>D] Record EFFECTOR system’s activity from PC : Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> <i>Description: Screenshots and/ or short videos recorded from computer’s screen during the operation of the EFFECTOR’s system</i></p>	

